

ANGLE CLOSURE GLAUCOMA IN INDIA- FAMILY PHYSICIANS CAN TAKE MAJOR ROLE

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Introduction

Headache is quiet common symptom in any physician chamber. Sometimes it is easy to establish a cause or many a times patient become cynical without etiology and empirical treatment. Usually these cases are commonly misdiagnosed as Migrain while migraine is always diagnosis of exclusion. Once referred to an eye clinic, refractive errors are important diagnosis but any form of glaucoma must be excluded by thorough eye examination.

Primary Angle Closure Glaucoma is quiet common in Indian and Asian population in contrast to Primary Open Angle Glaucoma in western population. Apart from being 'Silent thief of Sight' it creates many episodes of discomfort in daily works as headache, colour haloes, nausea and non-specific symptoms like heaviness, browache and eyeache. Usually these patients are hypermetrope, females, anxious looking and having small axial length of eye. Gonioscopy and Anterior Segment OCT (Angle) is important tool in their diagnosis and counselling. Laser Peripheral Iridectomy (YAG Laser PI) is procedure of choice in treating and alleviating symptoms.

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Discussion

According to survey, estimated burden of Angle closure disease is 23 million out of 120 million population in India. It signifies that every one person is at risk out of 5 people in general population. 11 million people are suffering from Primary Angle Closure Glaucoma (PACG).

Angle closure can be primary or secondary.

Glaucoma is chronic progressive optic neuropathy with characteristic visual field defect with or without rise in Intraocular Pressure (IOP). Glaucoma in PACD does not happen at once except after acute congestive glaucoma which is an ocular emergency. It passes through stages of PACS to PAC and thereafter PACG. PACS people are usually asymptomatic and they don't report to eye clinic in beginning. Usually in initial stages, if symptomatic they do self-medications with NSAIDs for their non-specific symptoms, later present to family physicians. Family physicians should take

major role in such cases with their proximity to family ascertaining etiology and treatment. It is always rewarding to keep a diagnosis of Migraine at end after proper ocular examination with Gonioscopy, Refraction and IOP measurement along with diagnostic fundus examination. Many of these patients are diagnosed early on referral to ophthalmologists and is quiet curative in non-specific symptoms and preventive in blinding PACG.

Ocular examinations with baseline recording of all parameters are boon to patients and their treating family physicians. Imaging investigations e.g; Anterior Segment OCT and Ultrasound Biomicroscopy (UBM) are important tool in establishing diagnosis and counselling. They make the person to understand the diseases and choosing Laser PI treatment as prophylactic procedure to save many productive days to humanity. Laser PI has replaced Surgical PI in today's era because of Day Care OPD Procedure, minimum interference to life styles and effectivity.

There may be different school of thoughts for Laser PI in PACS patients but it should not be denied to symptomatic, hypermetropic, female patients having frequent episodes of headache and so called migraine symptoms. Laser PI also prevents progression to PAC and PACG to prevent blindness from glaucoma. Laser PI is indicated at earliest in cases of PAC and PACG to halt progression of diseases and also topical antiglaucoma medications to act properly.

Summary and Conclusion

Angle closure disease is important differential in Headache before making diagnosis of Migrain and appropriate diagnosis and effective treatment can be done to save many productive work-years and prevention of blindness.

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